

Thinking about the contributor retention trend dashboard, how likely are you to use the following information for your project. Please briefly explain

- Trends of **contributors joining** and their details

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Trends of contributors that **might be leaving** and their details

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Trends of contributors who **left**

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Percentage of contributors who left by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Percentage of contributors who left by gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Is there any other way you would use the retention trend dashboard that we did not cover? Is there any other information you would like to see in this dashboard?

